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Supplementary material for
**Magnitude-Corrected and Time-Aligned
Interpolation of Head-Related Transfer Functions**
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Contents

1	HRIRs and HRTFs in the horizontal plane	1
2	Magnitude correction filters	2
3	Differences between individual and dummy head HRTFs	4
4	Magnitude errors for measured HRTFs	5
5	Marginal means for source type × method	5
6	Log-spectral difference	6
7	Stimuli listening experiment	6

1 HRIRs and HRTFs in the horizontal plane

Figure S1: Simulated left ear HRIRs (top) and HRTFs (bottom) of HUTUBs subject 91 in the horizontal plane. Azimuth angles of 0° , 90° , 180° , and 270° denote source positions in front, to the left, at the back, and to the right of the subject.

2 Magnitude correction filters

Frequency-averaged absolute magnitude of the left-ear correction filters C over 900 directions of the target Fliege grid for simulated HRTFs of subject no. 91 from the HUTUBS database. The Figures S2-S4 below show results for different combinations of interpolation and alignment approaches. As sparse sampling grid, we used a Lebedev grid with 26 points (SH order $N = 3$). (SU_pDEq - Spatial Upsampling by Directional Equalization, PC - Phase Correction, OBTA - Onset-Based Time-Alignment, SH - Spherical Harmonics, NN - Natural Neighbor)

Figure S2: SU_pDEq alignment with SH interpolation (left) and NN interpolation (right).

Figure S3: PC alignment with SH interpolation (left) and NN interpolation (right).

Figure S4: OBTA alignment with SH interpolation (left) and NN interpolation (right).

Frequency-dependent signed magnitude of the left-ear correction filters C over the horizontal plane for simulated HRTFs of subject no. 91 from the HUTUBS database. The Figures S5-S7 below show results for different combinations of interpolation and alignment approaches. As sparse sampling grid, we used a Lebedev grid with 26 points (SH order $N = 3$). (SUPDEq - Spatial Upsampling by Directional Equalization, PC - Phase Correction, OBTA - Onset-Based Time-Alignment, SH - Spherical Harmonics, NN - Natural Neighbor)

Figure S5: SUPDEq alignment with SH interpolation (left) and NN interpolation (right).

Figure S6: PC alignment with SH interpolation (left) and NN interpolation (right).

Figure S7: OBTA alignment with SH interpolation (left) and NN interpolation (right).

3 Differences between individual and dummy head HRTFs

Figure S8: Comparison of all individual simulated HRTFs from the HUTUBS database against the simulated HRTFs of the FABIAN dummy head from the HUTUBS database. Top: Direction-averaged magnitude error $\Delta G(f_c, s)$ and frequency-, direction-, and subject-averaged left-ear magnitude error ΔG (in text box). Middle: Horizontal plane ILD error $\Delta \text{ILD}(\Omega, s)$ and direction- and subject-averaged ILD error ΔILD (in text box). Bottom: Horizontal plane ITD error $\Delta \text{ITD}(\Omega, s)$ and direction- and subject-averaged ITD error ΔITD (in text box). Gray lines show results for individual subjects; black lines shows mean error; blue lines mean error \pm the standard deviation across subjects; red lines show the corresponding just noticeable difference.

4 Magnitude errors for measured HRTFs

Figure S9: Magnitude error $\Delta G \pm SD$ across subjects for simulated HUTUBS HRTFs as well as ΔG for measured HRTFs of the KU100 dummy head [1] and FABIAN head-and-torso simulator [2].

5 Marginal means for source type \times method

Figure S10: Marginal means of the ratings as a function of source type (abscissa) and method (color) for the four attributes. The error bars display 95% within-subjects confidence intervals [3], based on the error term of the respective main effect of method.

6 Log-spectral difference

Table S1: Frequency-, direction-, and subject-averaged left-ear log-spectral difference (LSD) and standard deviation across subjects in dB for SH orders $N = 1 - 10$. SUpDEq-processed SH interpolation with magnitude correction (MCA interpolation).

SH Order N	Num. of points (Lebedev)	LSD _{f_{c_1}}	LSD _{f_{c_2}}
1	6	5.46 (0.37)	4.96 (0.40)
2	14	4.51 (0.31)	4.02 (0.31)
3	26	3.84 (0.29)	3.37 (0.27)
4	38	3.37 (0.26)	2.94 (0.23)
5	50	2.97 (0.24)	2.56 (0.20)
6	74	2.91 (0.23)	2.50 (0.19)
7	86	2.37 (0.20)	2.03 (0.16)
8	110	2.13 (0.18)	1.81 (0.14)
9	146	1.92 (0.16)	1.62 (0.13)
10	170	1.76 (0.15)	1.49 (0.12)

Note. LSD _{f_{c_1}} - entire audible frequency range from 20 Hz to 20 kHz; LSD _{f_{c_2}} - frequency range from 20 Hz to 16 kHz for comparison with [4]

7 Stimuli listening experiment

The zip file `Stimuli_Experiment.zip` contains the binaural renderings in the form of WAV files as used in the listening experiment. For more information on how the stimuli were generated and how the listening experiment was conducted, please refer to the accompanying paper.

Please note that the binaural renderings are intended for headphone listening and are diffuse-field equalized, which means that they do not required additional headphone compensation filters.

References

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